

DETERMINANTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION AIMED AT THE DEVELOPMENT OF MECHANISMS OF ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article presents an analysis of the literature on the topic, determinants, description of the determinants of environmental education, aimed at developing mechanisms for environmental education in higher education.

Keywords: determinants, environmental education, environmental education, environmental consciousness, environmental competence, environmental safety.

In the process of human activity, ensuring his environmental education is one of the urgent socio-pedagogical issues today. Recently, it has been studied as a separate research object not only in pedagogy, but also in philosophy, political science, psychology, sociology, medicine, law, economics, military, technical sciences.

The impact of production enterprises on the external environment is especially evident in the world of plants. This causes changes in the growth, development and loss of plants. In this regard, N.P. Abaskalova studied the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle as a safety factor [1]. I. Anyugin, R. Durnev, V. Slomyansky, E. Taminkina, M. Fakhрутдинov [2] considered the educational technologies necessary for the future activities of students in the field of environmental crisis prevention. While V. Kazakov[3] studied the issues of formation of environmental culture in students using role-playing games, I.N. Nemkova[4] studied the problem of transmitting information related to ecology provided to students in higher education.

And G.A. Popova considered methodological approaches in teaching the science of "Safety of life activities" for students of pedagogical and humanistic directions of undergraduate education, assuming the reduction of classroom lecture hours and the increase of independent work hours[5], T.I. Tarasova [6] developed a methodology for directing students to volunteer organizations.

T.S. Nazarova, B.C. Shapovalenko[7] revealed the theoretical issues of presenting environmental knowledge to students and studied the basics of environmental safety. B.I.Mishin, Yu.V.Repin, A.Smirnov developed the concept of the "Basics of Life Safety" course. I. D. Zverev studied the integrative relationship of environmental knowledge in modern school conditions [8,9,10,11].

Analysis of sources published in recent years shows that the need to understand environmental determinants is one of the main motivations of people and communities. Accordingly, in this article we aim to provide a description of the determinants:

Determinants are environmental conditions, reasons, factors associated with the development of a person. In literature on pedagogy and psychology, determinants (D.B.Elkonin, Sh.Abdullaeva, N.V.Pavlova) are evaluated as a special quality acquired by a person in the process of interaction and communication in the socio-cultural environment[12,13,14]. In the field of modern science, the determinants of personality development are considered from the point of view of biogenetic, sociogenetic and personogenetic directions of human knowledge. Representatives of the biogenetic direction focus on the anthropogenetic characteristics of a person (tendency, temperament, biological age, gender, body type, neurodynamic properties of the nervous system, organic motivation, movement, need). These characteristics, according to representatives of this approach, go through different stages of maturity in ontogeny.

As a result of the analysis of literature and Internet data, the following are among the determinants of ecological education aimed at the development of mechanisms of ecological education in higher education:

Ecological education is a process aimed at increasing the knowledge and intellectual potential of nature, aimed at educating in the spirit of love for mother nature and its benefits. For centuries, the issues of preserving nature, using its resources without allowing wastage, ensuring human health and appealing to nature's unbiased help in this process have been in the attention of advanced people of society, especially scholars.

Environmental education - the importance of environmental education in the modern world is not in doubt, and it is the priority direction of education and training in many countries. Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Nature Protection" states that "... ecological education is compulsory in all types of educational institutions", and the main goal of environmental education is to protect the environment at all levels of the population, including secondary school and college students and higher education students. is to form a conscious attitude to problems. The more ecological knowledge is formed from a young age, the more effective such education will be. Therefore, the scientific organization of this process is supported by the state.

Ecological consciousness - goal-oriented practical activities of all citizens, including young people, in the field of nature protection is a necessary condition for the formation of individual ecological consciousness. Ecological awareness embodies knowledge and belief in the field of human interaction with nature. Ecological knowledge is an important condition for people to understand how integrally they are connected with the present and future biosphere, the objective necessity of nature protection, rational use of natural resources, education of the sense of responsibility for the state of the environment in every person, preservation of animal and plant life.

Ecological culture is the conscious attitude of a person to nature and its blessings, the formation of an active life perspective on nature protection for the Mother Earth. This activity, aimed at forming the ecological culture of the population and a careful attitude to the environment, is a guarantee of the future

safety of all mankind. Today, the processes of integration of all levels of social consciousness and forms of culture within the framework of ecological interests are being intensified. The modern world is going through such a period that the education of ecological culture among young people has become one of the actual directions of educational activity.

Ecological competence - acquisition of theoretical ecological knowledge in the formation of ecological consciousness, culture, having understanding of nature, land, water, flora and fauna, natural resources and being able to communicate about them, respect for nature, being able to use natural resources wisely, ecological education and to acquire the skills of wide use of all effective forms and methods of cultural and educational work in the direction of environmental education, including mass media, verbal, visual and technical means. Maintaining the balance between the ever-increasing needs of mankind and the diminishing opportunities on our planet, having ecological knowledge to protect nature is a sign of ecological competence.

Environmental security is a state of activity with the goal of eliminating the occurrence of environmental hazards with a certain probability[15]. The concept of security is multifaceted and interpreted in different ways. Nevertheless, they also have a common idea, according to which security is protection and guarantee from the dangers that arise in various spheres of human life, that is, security means the protection and provision of the vital interests of the individual, society and the state from external and internal threats with constitutional, legal and practical measures. Thus, our analysis of the historical-philosophical and social changes of the determinants of "ecological education", "ecological education", "ecological consciousness", "ecological competence", "ecological security" shows that throughout the history of mankind, the vector of "destruction concept" has been external the actions of external forces affecting the effect (natural disasters, epidemics, invasion of invaders, etc.), changes have occurred in relation to inward-looking fears, that is, fear of man. It is known that the inviolability of life is the main

way to eliminate the destructive beginnings hidden in the human person, in the depths of his personality.

The highest level of human thinking is ecological thinking. A person should be self-aware, always have a conscious attitude towards nature and instill the same mentality in others, that is, he should be aware of the consequences of any behavior that may have a negative impact on nature in our daily life and act accordingly, have relevant knowledge and skills, every it is necessary to understand that the citizen is an inseparable part of nature and its savior. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms of ecological education at all levels of education.

References:

1. Абаскалова Н.П. Безопасность жизнедеятельности // Учебно-методическое пособие.-Новосибирск, 2014.-72 с.
2. Анюгин И., Дурнев Р., Сломянский В., Таминкина Е. Фахрутдинов М. Образовательные технологии в области защиты от ЧС // Основы безопасности жизнедеятельности. — 2012. № 1. — С. 54-57.
3. Казаков В. Игры, похожие на жизнь (формирование личности безопасного типа с использованием ситуационных ролевых игр на уроках ОБЖ) // Основы безопасности жизни. — 2000. № 6. - С. 17-19.
4. Немкова И.Н. Формирование культуры безопасности жизнедеятельности студентов в процессе профессиональной подготовки в вузе. Автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук. Елец-2005.
5. Попова Г.А. Непрерывное образование: цели, задачи, содержание, функции, перспективы развития // Проблемы и перспективы развития образования: материалы VI междунар. науч. конф. (г. Пермь, апрель 2015 г.). — Пермь: Меркурий, 2015. –С.40-41.
6. Тарасова Т.И, Тихонова А.Э. Экологическое воспитание в образовательных учреждениях.-М.:Радуга,2011.-212с.

7. Назарова Т.С., Шаповаленко В. Так о чем же этот курс? О Сущности концептуальной проблемы курса ОБЖ // Основы безопасности жизни. – М.:2000. №6, С.9-14.

8. Мишин Б.И. Образование как фактор обеспечения личной, общественной и государственной безопасности // Образование и безопасность: проблемы, концепции, реальность: Материалы Всероссийской конференции / -М.: 2002. 84- 85 с.

9. Репин Ю.В. Гуманистическая концепция курса “Основы безопасности жизнедеятельности”: Автореф.дисс.к.п.н. – Екатеринбург. 2002. -26с.

10. Смирнов А.Т. Педагогические условия формирования основ безопасности жизнедеятельности учащихся общеобразовательных школ России: Автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук. М., 2011. – С.17.

11. Зверев И.Д., Максимова В.Н. Межпредметные связи в современной школе.-М.: Педагогика, 1981.-158с.

12. Эльконин Д.Б. Педагогическая психология.-М.:Владос, 2011.-286с.

13. Абдуллаева Ш.А., Нусратова Х., Абдуллаев Ф. Педагогика: Нодирабегим, 2021.-210-б.

14. Павлова Н.В. Тувельман А.Е., Скегина Н.Г. Интеграция тем программы “Здоровье” в предметы учебного плана // Школа здоровья. — 2001. — № 3. — С. 35-51.;

15. Райимов Ш.К. Олий ўқув юрти талабаларида огоҳлик ва фидойилик маданиятини шакллантиришнинг педагогик асослари. Пед.фан.ном.дис. – Фарғона, 2007. -139 б.;

16. Mamajonov Shukhratjon Askarovich “Environmental competence: theoretical and methodological approaches” EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD) Volume: 7 | Issue: 11 | November 2022, SJIF Impact Factor 2022: 8.197| ISI I.F. Value: 1.241| Journal DOI: 10.36713/epra2016 ISSN: 2455-7838(Online)58-60 betlar.

17. Sh.A.Mamajonov Talabalarda ekologik kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishning pedagogik hususiyatlari, “Kimyo va kimyo ta’limi muammolari” mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy – amaliy anjuman materiallari to’plami, 534-536 betlar 2022-yil 20-sentabr QDPI.

18. Mamajonov Shukhratjon Askarovich “Mweltkompetenz als ziel und ergebnis moderner bildung” Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities ISSN 2749-0866 Vol.2 Issue 1.5 Pedagogical sciences <http://berlinstudies.de/> 825-830 betlar.

19. Mamajonov Sh.A. “Ekologik tarbiyani - ijtimoiy kelib chiqish asoslari”, “Kimyo va kimyo ta’limi muammolari” mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy – amaliy anjuman materiallari to’plami, 548-551 betlar 2022-yil 20-sentabr QDPI

20. Мамажонов Шухратжон Асқарович, Одилхўжазода Нигорахон Бахтиёрхўжа қизи, Жўраев Хусниддин Мухаммадалиевич “Олий таълим муассасалари кимё ўқитувчиларининг экологик компетентлик даражасини ривожлантириш”, Таълим ва инновацион тадқиқотлар 2022 йил №9 170-176 бетлар.

21. Мамажонов Шухратжон Асқарович, Нишонов Миркозимжон, Махсудова Гулнорахон Мухаммаджоновна “Экологик билимларни шакллантиришнинг атроф-мухит муҳофазасини амалга оширишдаги аҳамияти” Педагогика 2022, 4-сон, 34-37 бетлар.

22. Мамажонов Шухратжон Асқарович “Олий таълимда экологик тарбияни такомиллаштириш масалалари”, “Биоорганик кимёнинг долзарб муаммолари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий ва илмий-техник анжуман материаллари, Фарғона, 2021 йил 23 ноябр, 747-752 бетлар.

23. Mamajonov Shuxratjon Asqarovich “Talabalarda ekologik madaniyatni rivojlantirish ekologik xavfsizlik garovidir” “Biologiyada zamonaviy tadqiqotlar muammo va yechimlar” Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to’plami II qism 156-159 betlar, Termiz davlat universiteti 2022 11-12 oktabr

24. Mamajonov Shuxratjon Asqarovich “Ekologik Ta’lim –Ekologik Xavfsizlik Omili” Biologiyada zamonaviy tadqiqotlar muammo va yechimlar” Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to’plami II qism, 159-161 betlar Termiz davlat universiteti 2022 11-12 oktabr

25. Askarovich, M. S. THE USE OF FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN CHEMISTRY CLASSES. *Chief Editor*.

26. Askarovich, M. S., Qizi, O. N. B., & Kizi, M. I. B. (2021). FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF CHEMISTRY. *Вестник науки и образования*, (6-3 (109)), 28-31.

27. Askarovich, M. S., Uljaevna, U. O., & Inomjohnovna, O. N. (2020). Applying case study-method in teaching chemistry. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 62-64.

28. Mirkozimjon, N. (2021). PREPARING FUTURE CHEMISTRY TEACHERS TO INTRODUCE REPRODUCTION.

29. Mirzakarimovich, M. Y., & Nishonov, M. (2022). Studying the Efficiency of Teaching the Chemical Technology Course Using Information Technologies. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 13.

30. Mirzakarimovich, Y. M. (2022). UNIVERSITETLARDA KIMYOVIY TEXNOLOGIYA KURSINI OQITISHDA MULTIMEDIYA VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 20(1), 140-144.

31. Nishonov, M., Mamajonov, S., & Tojimamatov, D. (2022). METHODOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING THE MIGRATION OF MICROELEMENTS IN WATER AND SOILS. *American Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(07), 10-14.

32. Nishonov, M., Mamajonov, S., & Tojimamatov, D. (2022). Methodological Significance of Studying Chemical Pollution of the Environment by Microelements. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 10, 55-58.

33. Shermukhammadov, B. (2022). Creativity of a Teacher in an Innovative Educational Environment. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 22(12), 127.

34. Shuxratjon, M. S. A. S. M. (2022). BO ‘LAJAK MUTAXASSISLARNING KASBIY KOMPETENTLIGINI

RIVOJLANTIRISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI. *SCIENTIFIC APPROACH TO THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 1(5), 177-180.

35. Ахмедов, Б. А. (2020). Сиддиков Бахтиёр Саидкулович, Джалалов Бахромжон Бегмурзаевич МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ-ОСНОВНОЙ ФАКТОР В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ. *Academy*, 9, 60.

36. Ахмедов, Б. А., Сиддиков, Б. С., & Джалалов, Б. Б. (2020). МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ-ОСНОВНОЙ ФАКТОР В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ КОМПЕТЕНЦИИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ. *Academy*, (9 (60)), 20-22.

37. Мамажонов, Ш. А., & Кизи, О. Н. Б. (2019). Формирование профессиональной компетенции преподавателя химии. *Вестник науки и образования*, (19-2 (73)), 31-33.

38. Мамажонов, Ш. А., & Одилхўжазода, Н. Б. (2021). Бўлажак кимё ўқитувчиларининг компетентлигини шакллантириш технологиялари ва мезонлари. *НамДУ илмий ахборотномаси*, 437-438.

39. Нишонов, М., Абдуллажонов, Х., Хайдаров, А. А., & Собиров, А. О. (2019). Инновационный подход к обучению курса «химия» в направлении «технология пищевых продуктов». *Universum: технические науки*, (12-2 (69)), 33-36.

40. Шермухаммадов, Б. (2012). Использование различных методов, форм и средств в воспитании молодежи. *Актуальные проблемы современной науки*, (5), 80-83.